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ABSTRACT

In this contribution a general purpose digitally controlled analog filter is presented. The novel design is a cascade of second order sections that are individually programmed to achieve any filtering topologies. Two-binary words are used to control the pole frequency ω_p and selectivity Q_p of each section independently. Each second order section is a Generalized-Immittance converter (GIC) biquads which are known for their high stability and low active and passive sensitivity. CMOS switches are used to electronically relocate the minimum number of passive elements to achieve function programmability. Switches are also used to select the number of cascaded sections to realize higher order transfer functions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The availability of an analog filter with digitally controlled "programmable" coefficients has been the goal of many researchers due to its several attractions. One possibility of a compact, versatile analog filter under remote control opens up many novel and independent application areas. Also, when a programmable filter is combined with a permanent reference memory which is user-programmable, this would form an economical and versatile device for dedicated stand-alone applications. The need for such a device was motivated by advancement in film and semiconductor technologies as well as the continuous upgrading of systems specifications to take advantage of the available technologies to the limits.

Linear analog filtering finds many applications, such as speech processing (recognition or synthesis), geology, instrumentation, communications, process control, adaptive balancing, etc. There has been much emphasis on performing the filtering function digitally, largely because of the ease of varying and optimizing the transfer function. However, for many reasons, such as cost, size, signal processing complexity, and bandwidth, it would be desirable to perform the filter function with linear components yet retain the flexibility of varying the filter parameters digitally.

Recently, the advantages of combining linear components (operational amplifiers (OAS),

resistors and capacitors) and nonlinear elements (switches) have been demonstrated using switched capacitor techniques [1-3]. In this contribution, we are presenting the results of realizing a continuous active device using linear elements and switches controlled by digital signals to achieve a fully programmable filter [4]. Several programming features of the proposed filter are reported. The first feature is the ability of the network to realize the most common filtering functions (function programmability) namely: Low Pass (LP), Band Pass (BP), High Pass (HP), All Pass (AP) and Notch(N) functions, using the minimal set of elements. The second feature is the ability of the network to program (independently) the key parameters of the filtering function chosen (parameter programmability) namely: the pole resonant frequency (ω_p) and selectivity (Q_p). Finally the ability to program the network to cascade several sections to achieve higher order filter. All of the above programmability features are performed independently to realize a universal filtering network.

2. DESIGN ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED FILTERS

The basic active network considered here as the heart of the programmable filter is the second order Generalized Immittance Converter (GIC) structure [5], Fig. 1, whose superior performance was established in the literature [6]. The general transfer function realized $T(s)$ is given by:

$T(s) = N(s)/D(s) = (a_0 + a_1s + a_2s^2) / (b_0 + b_1s + b_2s^2)$ (1)
 The GIC transfer functions of Fig. 1 assuming non-ideal OAs are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1 \left[1 + \frac{s}{w_2} \right] + \frac{y_3}{w_2} s & & y_3 & & -y_3 - y_1 & & \\ & & & & & & \\ y_2 \left[1 + \frac{s}{w_2} \right] + \frac{s}{w_2} [y_5 + y_6] & & -\frac{s}{w_1} [y_2 + y_5 + y_6] & & -y_2 - y_5 - y_6 & & \\ & & & & & & \\ 0 & & y_4 & & -y_4 - y_7 - y_8 & & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_1(s) \\ \\ T_2(s) \\ \\ T_3(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \\ -y_5 \\ \\ -y_7 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Stability and sensitivity analysis:

An important criterion of a realization is its sensitivity to element variations. The GIC sensitivity analysis has shown to be as good or better than all competitive second order networks [6]. While the GIC stability can easily be demonstrated since in all the transfer functions (2), the coefficients of $D(s)$ are seen to remain positive for any OA mismatch. This is

due to the absence of negative terms in $D(s)$. Therefore the zeros of $D(s)$ will remain in the left-half s -plane and low frequency unstable modes cannot arise during activation.

Function programmability:

The objective of this research was to develop a device that is capable of realizing the following transfer functions: LP where $T(s) = K/D(s)$, BP where $T(s) = KS/D(s)$, HP where $T(s) = KS^2/D(s)$, AP where $T(s) = [s^2 - s(\omega_p/Q_p) + \omega_p^2]/D(s)$ and N where $T(s) = (s^2 + \omega_z^2)/D(s)$. By optimizing the design of the filter, it was found that all of the above functions can be realized by the second order GIC section using four resistors, two capacitors and two OAs as shown in Table 1. These passive elements are connected to different nodes to achieve the various realizations. A set of CMOS bilateral switches controlled by digital binary word, are used to relocate the same elements in different ways to achieve the desired filtering functions according to Fig. 2. The truth table of the switches control logic is shown in Table 2, while Fig. 3 illustrates the corresponding minimized CMOS logic circuit used for passive elements relocation.

Parameter programmability:

While four of the resistors are equal and of value R each, the fifth resistor is the Q_p determining resistor and of value $R_q = RQ_p$. The two capacitors are equal and of value $c = 1/(\omega_p R)$ each. Two equal banks of capacitors are used to control ω_p . Each bank contains n binary-weighted capacitors connected in series with n CMOS switches as shown in Fig. 4. Using n bit binary word to control the switches, 2^n different values of c can be obtained that corresponds to 2^n different values of ω_p . Using a similar technique, the value of R_q can be controlled by an m bit digital word that yields 2^m different values of Q_p , as illustrated in Fig. 5. Thus, full independent control of the pole pair ω_p and Q_p are achieved by programming the digital words controlling the switches to obtain the corresponding c and R_q . The complete second order programmable filter is shown in Fig. 6.a. where the function programmability as well as the parameter programmability are demonstrated.

Higher order programmability:

Active filters design procedure can be classified as direct or cascade. In direct synthesis procedures the transfer function is realized as a single section [7]. In cascade synthesis procedures a high order transfer function is expressed as a product of first and second order transfer functions and each of these is realized independently. The overall network is obtained by cascading the individual sections. The cascade method of synthesis offers two practical advantages (a) simple network tuning (b) a few number of universal sections can be designed which can realize a multitude of network specifications.

The second order GIC network structure lends itself to the cascade synthesis procedure since it does not require additional isolating amplifiers. Fig. 6.b shows a block diagram of a programmable higher order filter that utilizes the second procedure by cascading 2 or more sections of the filter network shown in Fig. 6.a. The result is a high order fully programmable general purpose filter, that can be tailored to match almost any proposed specification.

3. COMPUTER SIMULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATIONS:

Fig. 7 shows different computer simulation outputs of the programmable filter. The plots simulate the filter responses assuming ideal OAs with infinite Gain Bandwidth Products (GBWP), as well as practical filter responses assuming OA's finite GBWPs of 1 MHz as of that of the LM741 OA. A single pole OA model was utilized to approximate the filter transfer functions in the later case. The approximation was found adequate since the simulation results of the nonideal response were found to be of close proximity to the experimental results of Fig. 8. The experimental results were obtained using a three bit word for filter topology programmability to select the type of transfer functions. A two words, four bits each, were used for filter parameters programmability where ω_p and Q_p are controlled independently as given in Table 3. Fig. 7 also illustrates a higher order programmability where a fourth order characteristics are shown for a LPF and a Chebychev BPF.

4. CONCLUSION

The novel design described here has resulted in a universal programmable filter that can be digitally controlled to realize almost any practical filter specifications. This is done through the use of CMOS switches controlled by binary codes to program the order of the filter, the filter topology, the filter center frequency and selectivity. The design procedure required developing optimum switching arrangements for the minimum redundancy in components and the least dependence of the filtering function on switching imperfections such as switches stray capacitances and non-zero and non-linear switch-on resistance. Further investigation is being conducted to develop a programmable switched capacitor realization that can allow frequency scaling by changing clock frequency. Work is also in progress for developing an extended bandwidth programmable filter using the composite operational amplifier technique proposed earlier by the author. Such implementation would lead to a very useful monolithic device at moderate cost.

5. REFERENCES

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switch control				Rq	Qp	switch control				C	Fp
Sa	Sb	Sc	Sd	K Ω		Sa	Sb	Sc	Sd	nF	KhZ
0	0	0	0	24.0	15	0	0	0	0	5.96	16.693
0	0	0	1	22.4	14	0	0	0	1	6.34	15.709
0	0	1	0	20.8	13	0	0	1	0	7.16	13.887
0	0	1	1	19.2	12	0	0	1	1	7.72	12.875
0	1	0	0	17.6	11	0	1	0	0	8.42	11.810
0	1	0	1	16.0	10	0	1	0	1	9.20	10.856
0	1	1	0	14.6	9	0	1	1	0	10.00	10.043
0	1	1	1	12.8	8	0	1	1	1	11.00	9.047
1	0	0	0	11.2	7	1	0	0	0	15.10	6.650
1	0	0	1	9.6	6	1	0	0	1	17.60	5.637
1	0	1	0	8.0	5	1	0	1	0	20.80	4.823
1	0	1	1	6.4	4	1	0	1	1	26.00	3.828
1	1	0	0	4.8	3	1	1	0	0	35.50	2.805
1	1	1	1	3.2	2	1	1	0	1	55.00	1.810
1	1	1	0	1.6	1	1	1	1	0	100.00	.995

Table 3. Binary Words Controlling Qp & fp

Fig. 1 The Generalized Immittance Converter

Filter Type	Y ₁	Y ₂	Y ₃	Y ₄	Y ₅	Y ₆	Y ₇	Y ₈	Transfer Function
LP	C	C	C + $\frac{C}{QP}$	G	G	0	0	G	$T_2 = 2Wp^2/D(s)$
HP	C	C	C	G	0	G	C	$\frac{G}{QP}$	$T_1 = 2S^2/D(s)$
BP	G	G	C	G	0	G	C	$\frac{C}{QP}$	$T_1 = 2(Wp/Qp)S/D(s)$
N	G	G	C	G	G	0	C	$\frac{G}{QP}$	$T_2 = (S^2 + W_n^2)/D(s)$
AL	G	G	C	G	G	0	C	$\frac{G}{QP}$	$T_1 = (s^2 - \frac{Wp}{QP}s + wp^2)/D(s)$

Table 1.

The Elements Values for Different Realizations

where $T(s) = N(s)/D(s)$ and $D(s) = s^2 + (Wp/Qp)s + wp^2$

To be Connected in Case of	Component Represented Realized	Node in Fig. 1	Component & Switches	Node in Fig. 1	Component Represented Realized	To be connected in case of
A, L, H, B, N	R ₂ , R ₅	(2)	R, S ₁ , S ₂	(1), (3)	R ₂ , R ₅	H, B, L, N, A
N, H, L, H, B	R ₆ , R ₈	(1)	R, S ₁ , S ₂ , S ₃ , S ₄	(2), (3), (4)	R ₆ , R ₈	H, B, N, A, L
L, H, B, N, A	C ₂ , C ₈	(2), (4)	C, S ₁ , S ₂ , S ₃ , S ₄ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₇	(1), (3), (4), (ND)	C ₂ , C ₇ , C ₈	L, H, N, A, B
L, H, B, N, A	RQ ₃ , RQ ₇ , RQ ₈	(1), (4)	RQ, S ₁ , S ₂ , S ₃ , S ₄ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₇ , S ₁₀	(2), (3), (4), (ND)	RQ ₃ , RQ ₇ , RQ ₈	L, B, H, N, A
H, B, A, L, N	T ₁ , T ₂	(1), (4)	S ₁ , S ₂ , S ₃ , S ₄ , S ₅ , S ₆ , S ₇ , S ₁₀	Output		L, H, B, N, A

Fig. 2 Elements Relocation Switches for topology programmability

Binary Input	Filter	Switch																															
		S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	S ₁₆	S ₁₇	S ₁₈	S ₁₉	S ₂₀	S ₂₁	S ₂₂	S ₂₃	S ₂₄	S ₂₅	S ₂₆	S ₂₇	S ₂₈	S ₂₉	S ₃₀		
0 0 0	Low Pass	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
0 0 1	High Pass	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
0 1 0	Band Pass	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
0 1 1	Notch	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
1 0 0	All Pass	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1

Table 2. The Truth Table of the Logic Controlling Elements Relocation Switches

Fig. 3 The logic controlling figure 2 switches

Fig. 4 Capacitors Banks for Frequency Programmability

(For linear Q_p control, $R_{j+1} = 2R_j$ resulting in $RQ_p = \sum_{j=0}^m R_0 b_j$)

Fig. 5 The Programmable R_q Resistor

Fig. 7.a

Ideal vs. nonideal L.P.F. amplitude response for frequencies (7.96K, 30.1K) and variety of Q_p .

Fig. 7.b

Ideal vs. nonideal L.P.F. amplitude response for $Q_p=2$ and frequencies (1.99K, 7.96K, 30.16K and 117.1K)

Fig. 7.c

Legend:
 --- Ideal
 — nonideal

Fig. 7.d

Fig. 7.e

Fig. 7.f

Fig. 6.a The General Second Order GIC Section

ORDER	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇
2	O	O	O	O	O	O	X
4	X	O	O	O	O	X	O
6	X	X	O	O	X	O	O
8	X	X	X	X	O	O	O

O: OPEN
 X: CLOSED

Fig. 6.b Higher Order Programmability of the GIC Sections

Fig. 7.g

Fig. 7.h

Fig. 7.k

Fig. 7.l

Fig. 7.m

Fig. 7.n

Fig. 7 Computer Simulation's Results.

Fig. 8.a

Fig. 8.b

2nd order & 4th order B.P.F

1. single
2. cascade
3. Chebychev by cascading BP - BP
f1 = 6.45K f2 = 12.9K
Q1 = 3 Q2 = 3.5

Fig. 8.c

B.P.F Realization for different frequencies

Fig. 8 Experimental Results